

THE BRANCHES OF TYPOLOGY ACCORDING TO THE CONNECTION OF LANGUAGE LAYERS AND THEIR TEACHING PROBLEMS

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Annotation: *This contribution is intended to summarise and exemplify important findings that have emerged from the systematic comparative study of sign languages over the last years. The increasing availability of data from diverse sign language around the world has made it possible, for the first time in the history of sign language research, to broaden our cross-linguistic data base sufficiently for meaningful typological studies across sign languages to be carried out. This new field of study is known as sign language typology.*

Keywords: *Typology, grammar, language, method, syntactic typology, theoretical typology.*

INTRODUCTION

The sections below look at the new sub-discipline of sign language typology from a variety of different angles. Rather than being a systematic, exhaustive account of the whole field of study, the aim of this article is to provide illustrative glimpses from different angles. Among others, we will look at the sources whose confluence creates the field of sign language typology (the “roots” in terms of the metaphor in the title), at the different ways of doing sign language typology and the associated methodologies (the “branches”) and at some of the fascinating data and their typological and theoretical significance (the “leaves”).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sign language typology draws upon two source disciplines within linguistics that previously had little contact one another. As the name already suggests, these two disciplines are sign language research and linguistic typology. The interaction between them is schematically illustrated in Figure 1, which shows the double orientation inherent in sign language typology: On the one hand, sign language typology uses theoretical and methodological resources from linguistic typology, but broadens the range of the available languages to include sign languages. Conversely, sign language typology uses results from sign language research, but focuses on linguistic diversity within the group of sign languages from a typological perspective.

Figure 1: The source disciplines of sign language typology

As far as the entire range of linguistic sub-disciplines in spoken language research is concerned, no field is more naturally predestined to having an avid interest in sign languages than the field of linguistic typology. By and large, since coming into existence in the second half of the 20th century,

linguistic typology has been concerned with evaluating how languages are different from or similar to one another.

The second topic that lies at the heart of linguistic typology and is closely related to the first one, somewhat like the flipside of the same coin, is the search for language universals (e.g. Comrie 1989, Whaley 1997, Song 2001). What is it really that all languages have in common and that, therefore, can be said to define the true nature of human language? More than for any other research question, it is immediately obvious here that typologists must be most interested in what sign language research has to say about a totally different type of visual-gestural language that has not been considered before.

Just as typologists have previously ignored sign languages for the most part, sign language researchers have also not taken into account a typologically informed perspective on their data. However, there is much to gain from such a perspective, as will become clear in section 3 below. Indeed, the true extent of linguistic diversity across sign languages only becomes apparent when a typological angle is applied to both known and newly discovered data, and these results continue to surprise even experienced sign linguists.

Despite the clear connection between sign language typology and its two source domains, we are not dealing merely with a merger of the two other fields. Rather, sign language typology brings with it an entire new set of research questions and methodologies. These are detailed in sections 2.2 and 2.3 respectively.

Sign language typology has two related immediate aims, both of which are associated with different methodologies. The detailed documentation of individual sign languages around the world broadly overlaps with corresponding descriptive research in sign linguistics, but has a somewhat different focus. On the other hand, the systematic cross-linguistic study of

broad samples of genetically and geographically unrelated sign languages is a new undertaking that has no previously existing parallels in sign linguistics, but is in many ways similar to corresponding work in spoken language typology. These two types of investigation are intended to lead to a theory of variation across sign languages, which is the most important secondary aim of sign language typology. Accounting for the patterns of differences and similarities across sign languages then also allows us to re-assess the question of language universals that hold both for sign languages and for spoken languages, as well as the question of modality differences between sign languages on the one hand and spoken languages on the other hand. Figure 2 shows a flow chart of inter-relatedness of the main academic aims in sign language typology. The non-academic aims of sign language typology research are detailed in section 5 of this paper.

Figure 2: The aims of sign language typology

The most recent important addition to the sign language data mosaic consists of sign languages in village communities (see the purple trapeze in Figure 3).

Figure 3: The mosaic of sign language data

For the purpose of sign language typology, not all kinds of linguistic documentation are equally valuable. The most important type of documentation is a reference grammar. Reference grammars are concise, yet in-depth accounts of all grammatical structures found in a language,

and they are an important source of information for spoken language typologists, who can rely on several hundred reference grammars, though not all of equal quality. However, to date sign language research has not produced a single reference grammar on any sign language, so the sign language typologists has to rely on other, less than ideal, sources.

In order to arrive at a theory of variation across sign languages, it is necessary to make generalisations over comparable data from a wide range of sign languages. It is essential that these generalisations should be empirically substantiated, that is, based on real evidence from a range of primary data, rather than based on deductive reasoning and/or assumptions based on very few or even a single sign language. Cross-linguistic studies on sign languages address research questions about the *parameters* of variation that we can find across sign languages, about the *range* of variation that is displayed, and about *patterns* of variation.

CONCLUSION

For sign language typology, it is important to look for functional explanations of both similarities and differences across sign languages. Often the previous findings of spoken language typology can be of use here. For instance, the close relationship between interrogatives and indefinites, or between possession and existence, has been found in both spoken and sign languages, and explanations for these patterns have been suggested in the spoken language typology literature. Inventories of patterns, such as a limited number of construction types used to express possession (as in Heine 1997) can often be applied to sign languages as well.

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